

Annual Water Balance Model of the Upper Colorado River Basin

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ABSTRACT

Everything should be as simple as possible and no simpler.
Albert Einstein as paraphrased by Roger Sessions

Numerical simulation of conditions in the Colorado River System has been central to decisions about operation and planning of the system for over 50 years. Numerical models are used to simulate the movement of water through the massive and complex infrastructure of the basin and along the natural waterways that connect elements of that infrastructure, subject to constraints placed on water movement and use by the equally complex body of compacts, treaties, federal and state statutes, court decisions and decrees, contracts, and regulations that make up what is called the “Law of the River”.

The canonical model of the Colorado River System is the Colorado River Simulation System, developed and maintained by the U.S. Bureau of Reclamation. CRSS is, unsurprisingly, as complex as the river system itself. As such, its careful application requires a considerable devotion of time to learn the modeling system and to configure it for different analyses.

The Upper Basin Water Balance Model described here is just about as simple as a model of the Colorado River System can be, an annual, single-reservoir model. It is offered as a complement to CRSS as a tool that is easy to understand, and thus to apply and modify, in order to investigate alternative conditions, policies and practices, and that is efficient, so that simulations of long traces and large ensembles of long traces are feasible.

Explicit concerns that consumptive use in the Upper Division states might be limited by the obligations imposed on the states by Article III(c) and Article III(d) of the Colorado River Compact seem first to have surfaced publicly 70 years ago in a 1953 report by Raymond Hill (Hill, 1953) to the Colorado Water Conservation Board, acknowledged by the Board in 1955 (CWCB, 1955) and reiterated by Hill in a 1961 report to the Attorney General of California (Hill, 1961). This concern was stated more prominently by Royce J. Tipton in his report of 1965 for the Colorado Water Conservation Board (Tipton, 1965a) and his statement to Congress in the same year in the context of the debate about authorization of the Central Arizona Project (Tipton, 1965b).

The first reservoir models used in the Colorado River System were likely operations models, implemented with pencil, paper and calculators. These were implemented in computer code in the mid-1960's and adapted for

planning purposes before the end of that decade. See Harding (2024a) for a more complete, but still brief history of simulation of the Colorado River System.

Over time, those computer codes evolved and consolidated into the current canonical model of the system, the Colorado River Simulation System (CRSS), developed as an implementation of the RiverWare™ generalized river basin modeling tool, which in turn was developed by Reclamation, in collaboration with the Tennessee Valley Authority and working with the Center for Advanced Decision Support in Water and Environmental Systems, CADSWES, at the University of Colorado). CRSS has been used operationally by Reclamation since 1996.

CRSS is, unsurprisingly, as complex as the river system itself, perhaps even more complex: RiverWare™ is a rule-based simulation system and CRSS contains about 200 rules (Carron, 2024), many of which interact with other rules. Changing one rule requires a good understanding of these interactions and their effect. Without that understanding, changes to rules can cause unexpected behavior leading to unexpected results. As such, its careful application requires a considerable devotion of time to learn the modeling system and to configure it for different analyses. This is especially true when it comes to modifying assumptions about elements of the Law of the River.

The Upper Colorado Water Balance model (“UBWB Model”) described here is just about as simple as a model of the Colorado River System can be, an annual, single-reservoir model. It is offered as a complement to CRSS as a tool that is easy to understand, and thus to apply and modify in order to investigate alternative conditions, policies and practices, and that is efficient, so that simulation of long traces and large ensembles of long traces is feasible.

The simulation approach and codes used in the UBWB Model are an automation of the annual water balance method used in the U.S. Bureau of Reclamation’s 2007 Hydrologic Determination (2007HD, Reclamation, 2007a). See Section 2. It is an adaptation of the model developed for and used in the Colorado River Water Availability Study (CWCB, 2012; Harding and Wheeler, 2010). That model was developed by reverse-engineering the results published in 2007HD. A similar approach, also based on 2007HD, was used in the Colorado River Water Bank Feasibility Study Phase 1 (Paulson, 2012) and curtailment risk studies undertaken by the Colorado River Water Conservation District.

The tradeoffs to simplicity are limitations on the suitability of the model for some applications, but it is suitable for the exploration of the sensitivity of water availability in the Upper Basin and of Lee Ferry flows to different assumptions about natural flow hydrology, Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use and policies.

It is a work in progress—this article discusses some enhancements that are envisioned, but readers and users will identify others, and they may identify errors in or areas for improvement of existing functionality. The author urges readers to provide comments on the model and on this article to his email address.

1 Colorado River Basin

The Colorado River basin drains approximately 250,000 square miles contained within the states of Colorado, Wyoming, Utah, New Mexico, Nevada, Arizona, California, and parts of the Mexican states of Baja, California and Sonora. The river is highly regulated by a total reservoir storage capacity approximately equal to four times the river's average annual flow.

The basin is divided both geographically and legally at Lee Ferry, just downstream of the point where the river crosses the Arizona-Utah border. The Upper Basin includes lands in the states of Colorado, New Mexico, Utah, and Wyoming, and a small amount of land in Arizona. The Upper Basin is the principal source of inflow into the Colorado River system. The Lower Basin includes lands in the states of Arizona, California, Nevada and New

Mexico. A lesser amount of inflow occurs in the Lower Basin, principally via the Little Colorado, Virgin, Bill Williams and Gila Rivers.

Many reservoirs alter the natural flow of the Colorado River. The two principal reservoirs, Lake Powell and Lake Mead, provide over 50 million acre-feet (maf) of storage. There are hundreds of reservoirs in the Upper Basin, above Lake Powell, but only slightly more than 60 with capacities above 4,000 acre-feet.

1.1 Hydrology

The record of gaged flows at Lees Ferry begins in 1922; estimates of depleted flows there have been extended back to 1896 using records from other gages. Reclamation maintains a record of estimated natural flows at Lees Ferry that begins in 1906 and is updated from time to time (Reclamation, 2024). Since the 1970s this record has been supplemented by long reconstructions of prehistoric flows and, since the 1990s, by ensembles of time series of projected flows affected by projected future climate conditions.

The natural flows in the basin are highly irregular in occurrence. While the annual natural flow at Lee Ferry has averaged about 15 maf over the period 1906 through 2020, annual natural flows in excess of 24 maf and less than 6 maf have been recorded.

1.2 Water Use

Water is diverted from the river at hundreds of relatively small diversions in the Upper Basin. These diversions benefit primarily from storage in local non-federal storage reservoirs, if they have access to stored water at all. The Lower Basin diversions tend to be larger and considerably fewer in number; diversions from the mainstem river in the Lower Basin are supplied from Lake Mead under water delivery contracts with the United States through the Secretary of the Interior under authority from the Boulder Canyon Project Act (1928, Nathanson, 1978). Shortages to uses along the Lower Basin mainstem are the result of operational policies at Lake Mead.

1.3 Water Resources Management

The Colorado River system is managed and operated in accordance with the “Law of the River”, which consists of compacts, treaties, federal and state statutes, court decisions and decrees, contracts, and regulations. See Wilbur and Ely (1933), Wilbur and Ely (1948), Nathanson (1978), MacDonnell, et al. (1995), and Verburg (2010). A comprehensive review is provided by MacDonnell (2021a) and a convenient compilation of digitized source documents is at Weisheit (2019). For a high-level summary, see Harding, 2024a

The Colorado River Compact (CRC, 1922) and the Upper Colorado River Basin Compact (UCRBC, 1948) are the elements of the Law of the River most relevant to the water balance in the Upper Basin. Provisions in the CRC, and to a lesser degree in the UCRBC constrain consumptive use of water in the Upper Basin.

Article III(c) of the CRC sets out terms by which a federal obligation under a treaty with Mexico, 1.5 maf, annually, would be shared between the Upper Division and the Lower Division--some portion of that federal delivery obligation may be the responsibility of the States of the Upper Division (Meyers, 1966; Robison, 2012).

Article III(d) of the CRC sets out the terms of an obligation on the states of the Upper Division not to cause the 10-year cumulative flow at Lee Ferry to be depleted below 75 maf. This requirement is not without controversy (Kenney, 2012; Kuhn, 2007; MacDonnell, 2021b).

Article VIII of the CRC exempts Present Perfected Rights (PPRs) in the Upper Basin from the apportionment and obligations set out in Article III. PPRs are state water rights that were perfected before the execution of the Compact.

Article III(a) of the CRC apportioned 7.5 maf of water to each of the Upper and Lower Basins but established the Article III(d) non-depletion requirement as an obligation of the Upper Division. At the time of its negotiation the view of the negotiators was that there would be ample water to meet that apportionment (along with an additional 1 maf granted to the Lower Basin, and some amount of water envisioned to be owed to Mexico). That view was substantially optimistic (Kuhn and Fleck, 2019), so the Articles III(c) and III(d) obligations serve as the principal constraint on the legal availability of water in the Upper Division.

In general terms, if the flow at Lee Ferry falls below the obligations set out in Article III(c) and Article III(d)--however these may eventually be interpreted--consumptive use in the Upper Division states must be curtailed to the degree necessary to offset any flow shortfall, except that Present Perfected Rights are not subject to curtailment. Article IV of the UCRBC sets out the terms by which consumptive use in the Upper Division states would be curtailed in the event of a flow shortfall. Herein, the term “curtailment” is used to refer to the concept of a cutback required by Article III(d) of the CRC and Article IV of the UCRBC, a particular curtailment event, and the amount of such a cutback.

The principal reservoir in the Upper Basin is Lake Powell, with a current active capacity of 20.3 maf, impounded behind Glen Canyon Dam, about 18 miles above Lee Ferry. Construction of Glen Canyon Dam, which closed in 1963, added another layer to the Law of the River in the form of operating rules: Criteria for Coordinated Long-Range Operation of Colorado River Reservoirs (LROC, Interior, 1970) formulated under the Colorado River Basin Project Act (1968), as subsequently updated (Verburg, 2010). The provision in the LROC for a “minimum objective release” is most relevant for simulating the system. See section 3.9.

In 2007, motivated by several years of drought and declining storage in the major reservoirs on the River, the Department of Interior established the Colorado River Interim Guidelines for Lower Basin Shortages and the Coordinated Operations for Lake Powell and Lake Mead (Interim Guidelines, Department of the Interior, 2007). For a more complete discussion of the Interim Guidelines, see Harding (2024a). See also Sections 3.9, 5.2 and 6.2.

2 The 2007 Hydrologic Determination Water Balance

The Hydrologic Determination water balance is an annual model of the water balance above Lee Ferry, including inflows, carryover reservoir contents, reservoir releases, reservoir evaporation, and Upper Basin consumptive use (2007HD). The Hydrologic Determination water balance is subject to the physical constraints on reservoir storage in the Upper Basin, assumptions about the non-depletion flow obligation at Lee Ferry, and assumptions about apportionment of the federal delivery obligation to Mexico. It covers a study period of 1906 through 2000 and is based on a record of annual natural flows over that period. It formally established that the yield to the Upper Basin is 5.76 maf. For more detail on the Hydrologic Determinations, especially the 2007 determination, see Harding (2024).

The Hydrologic Determination water balance model is a stepwise annual model involving five calculations (terms from 2007HD):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Water available to store} &= \text{CR Natural Flow at Lee Ferry} + \text{Total Carryover storage} \\ &\quad - \text{Lower Basin Delivery} - \text{Upper Basin Use} - \text{Shared CRSP Evap}; & (1) \\ \text{Spill to LC} &= \text{maximum}(0, \text{Water available to Store} - \text{Adjusted Storage (2060)}); & (2) \\ \text{Shortage} &= -\text{minimum}(0, \text{Water available to store}); & (3) \\ \text{UC Basin Year-end Storage} &= \text{Water available to store} - \text{Spill to LC} + \text{Shortage}. & (4) \\ \text{Total Carryover storage} &= \text{UC Basin Year-end Storage} & (5) \end{aligned}$$

The independent terms are:

- *CR Natural Flow at Lee Ferry*—An annual time series of natural inflows at Lee Ferry from 1906 through 2000. 2007HD describes this time series as being derived from the natural flow inputs to the Colorado River Simulation System (CRSS), with positive adjustments for flows during 1971-1980 to mitigate a reported error in estimates of Upper Basin consumptive use during that period. The inflows in 2007HD do not match the inflows over the same period from the natural flow database currently used in CRSS (Reclamation, 2024) for flows at either Lees Ferry or Lee Ferry. It is not possible to infer the basis for the flows in 2007HD.
- *Adjusted Storage (2060)*—A constant representing the total reservoir capacity available above Lee Ferry, assuming accumulated sediment as of 2060. If the power pools at Colorado River Storage Project (CRSP) units are assumed to be available for storage this variable is set to 33,833,590 af (live capacity); if the power pools are protected this variable is set to 29,530,030 af (active capacity). The numerical precision of these values are as shown in 2007HD.

Because the CRSP and non-CRSP reservoirs are lumped together they are assumed to be drawn down and filled in proportion.

- *Total Carryover storage*—I infer that at year one (1906 in 2007HD) this is initialized to *Adjusted Storage (2060)*. In each subsequent annual simulation Total Carryover storage is set equal to *UC Basin Year-end Storage* in the previous year (Equation 5).
- *Lower Basin Delivery*—This is a constant. In four simulations in 2007HD it is set to 8.25 maf; for the other four it is set to 7.50 maf. See Table 1. The former value is used for the final estimate of water availability adopted by the 2007 Hydrologic Determination. Both values represent an annualization of the two different assumptions about the flow obligation at Lee Ferry. The conventional assumption is that the flow obligation is the sum of the Article III(c) and the Article III(d) obligations, 8.25 maf. Note that the use of the values 7.50 maf and 8.25 maf for *Lower Basin Delivery* infer that the simulation is based on flows and obligations at Lee Ferry, but it is not possible to infer the basis for *CR Natural Flow at Lee Ferry*.
- *Upper Basin Use*—This is a constant representing the nominal demand for beneficial consumptive use of water in the Upper Basin (including non-CRSP reservoir evaporation). An annual value of *Upper Basin Use* adjusted for shortages (curtailed use) is not calculated in the Hydrologic Determination water balance, but the total shortage volume and total shortage percentage (calculated against *Upper Basin Use*) for the study period and for 1953–1977 and 1931–1977 are reported. The Hydrologic Determination water balance does not simulate local shortages in the Upper Basin.
- *Shared CRSP Evap*—This is the evaporation from CRSP reservoirs that is shared among the Upper Division States. It is limited to evaporation from Lake Powell, Flaming Gorge Reservoir, and the Aspinall Unit and excludes evaporation from Navajo Reservoir which is charged only to New Mexico because the supply from Navajo Reservoir is contracted for consumptive use only in that state and the reservoir is not currently available to meet Lee Ferry obligations. Intra-state reservoir evaporation is considered part of Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use.

2007HD documents two equations said to be used for calculating CRSP reservoir evaporation for each year (see 2007HD Appendix C), but values calculated using these equations do not match exactly the values reported in the water balance results (2007HD Appendix A). Regression of evaporation against average reservoir contents for Run 2 and for Run 6 gave slightly different relationships than those documented in Appendix C. Equation 6a is

the relationship inferred from the results of Run 2 of the 2007 Hydrologic Determination and is appropriate for use when simulating the use of active capacity. Equation 6b is the relationship inferred from the results of Run 6 of 2007HD and is appropriate for use when simulating the use of live capacity.

$$\text{Shared CRSP Evap} = 0.0209 \times \text{mean}(\text{Total Carryover storage, UC Basin Year-end Storage}) + 132877 \text{ af} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{Shared CRSP Evap} = 0.021292 \times \text{mean}(\text{Total Carryover storage, UC Basin Year-end Storage}) + 5017 \text{ af} \quad (6b)$$

The Hydrologic Determination reported eight runs covering a range of assumptions. Run 2 and Run 6 were used as the basis for this work. Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use does not include CRSP evaporation. Note that the formal determination in 2007HD was a yield to the Upper Basin of 5.76 maf, but the relevant runs simulated Upper Basin water use at 5.79 maf.

Table 1. Scenarios in 2007 Hydrologic Determination

Description	Adjusted Storage (2060) (af)	Lower Basin Delivery (af)	Upper Basin Use (af)	Number of shortage events (#)	1953-1977 Upper Basin Shortage (%)
Run 1 – Maintain CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 8.25 maf Lower Basin Delivery, No Shortage	29,530,030	8,250,000	5,550,000	0	0
Run 2 - Maintain CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 8.25 maf Lower Basin Delivery, 6% Overall Shortage	29,530,030	8,250,000	5,790,000	5	5.86
Run 3 - Maintain CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 7.50 maf Lower Basin Delivery, No Shortage	29,530,030	7,500,000	6,300,000	0	0
Run 4 - Maintain CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 7.50 maf Lower Basin Delivery, 6% Overall Shortage	29,530,030	7,500,000	6,570,000	5	5.86
Run 5 - Use CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 8.25 maf Lower Basin Delivery, No Shortage	33,833,590	8,250,000	5,720,000	0	0
Run 6 - Use CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 8.25 maf Lower Basin Delivery, 6% Overall Shortage	33,833,590	8,250,000	5,980,000	5	5.94
Run 7 - Use CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 7.50 maf Lower Basin Delivery, No Shortage	33,833,590	7,500,000	6,470,000	0	0
Run 8 - Use CRSP Minimum Power Pools, 7.50 maf Lower Basin Delivery, 6% Overall Shortage	33,833,590	7,500,000	6,760,000	5	5.92

3 Description of the Upper Basin Water Balance Model

The UBWB Model implements equations 1 – 5 and either equation 6a or 6b of 2007HD to perform an annual water balance at Lees Ferry. The single inflow is the natural flow at Lees Ferry. The outflows are Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use (“UB beneficial use”) which includes Upper Division PPRs and Arizona’s Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use; the Lee Ferry flow obligation; a portion of the Mexican Treaty delivery obligation; spills and shared CRSP reservoir evaporation.

The UBWB Model is adapted from the model used in the Colorado River Water Availability Study (CWCB, 2012). The code and data are available at Harding (2024b). It was validated against 2007HD as described in section 4.1. It is implemented in Python.

Table 2 lists the elements of the UBWB Model, along with their default values and methods and their basis. Any of these defaults can be modified. Descriptions of specific elements of the model follow.

Table 2. Elements of the UBWB Model

Element	Default Value and Basis
Lees Ferry inflows	User defined
Upper Basin reservoir capacity	29.53 maf (active capacity, 2007HD)
Reservoir evaporation	Equation 6a, Section 3.3 (2007HD)
Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use demand	7.59 maf per year (2007HD)
Upper Division Present Perfected Right demand	2.267 maf per year (Section 3.5; Kuhn, 2012)
Arizona beneficial consumptive use demand	0.05 maf per year (UCRBC)
Mexican Treaty obligation	0.75 maf per year (Mexican Treaty, CRC, convention)
Lee Ferry composite flow obligation	82.5 maf per 10 years (CRC, convention)
Glen Canyon minimum objective release	8.23 maf per year (Interior, 1970)

3.1 Lees Ferry Inflows

The simulation is forced with a time series of annual natural flows at Lees Ferry. The Lees Ferry gage is located approximately one mile above the mouth of the Paria River and approximately two miles above the compact division point at Lee Ferry. Flows at the Lees Ferry gage are assumed to be equal to flow below Glen Canyon Dam. Rather than adjust inflows to reflect the contribution of the Paria River, conventional practice, established with the LROC, has been to adjust the MOR and the Lee Ferry flow obligation to be consistent with measurement at Lees Ferry. Because Lees Ferry flows are used to force the UBWB Model, the obligation is simulated at Lees Ferry and is reduced by 0.02 maf per year (0.20 maf over the 10-year cumulative period), the average natural flow from the Paria River at its mouth, so that compliance with the Lee Ferry flow obligation can be assessed against Glen Canyon releases and spills.

3.2 Reservoir Capacity

All major reservoirs above Lee Ferry are assumed to be available to maintain flows past Lee Ferry, and are simulated as a single, lumped reservoir (2007HD Appendix B). 2007HD provides estimates of lumped reservoir active (capacity above the power pools) and live capacity (capacity above dead storage) in 2007 and in 2060, based on estimates of sediment accumulation. See section 2. The UBWB Model simulates active capacity as its default. Based on the user’s election of active or live capacity, the UBWB model sets the appropriate reservoir capacity volume and selects the appropriate evaporation function.

3.3 Evaporation

Under Article V(b)(1) of the 1948 UCRBC, evaporation from Lake Powell, Flaming Gorge Reservoir, and the Aspinall Unit is shared among the Upper Division states based on the states’ percentage compact shares set out in Article III(a)(2) (shared CRSP evaporation). Evaporation at all other Upper Basin reservoirs is considered part of each state’s share of UB beneficial use. 2007HD documents two equations used for calculating shared CRSP evaporation as a function of storage in the lumped reservoir, one for use when simulating active reservoir capacity (Equation 6a) and the second for use when simulating live reservoir capacity (Equation 6b). See Section 2. When the user elects to simulate the use of active capacity (the default option), Equation 6a is used to estimate reservoir evaporation; if live capacity is simulated Equation 6b is used.

An analysis of the published results of 2007HD (in Appendix A) determined that shared CRSP evaporation was based on the average of reservoir contents at the beginning and end of the year. Because year-end storage depends on the estimate of reservoir evaporation, an iterative approach is currently used for the annual simulation; referring to Section 2, equations 1-4 and 6a or 6b are iterated to convergence within a user-specified tolerance (default is 5 af) to determine year-end storage. Carryover storage is then set (Equation 5).

3.4 Upper Basin Beneficial Consumptive Use Demand

UB beneficial use is a constant parameter representing an estimate of the total annual amount of beneficial consumptive use in the Upper Basin, including beneficial consumptive use under present perfected rights and the fixed 50,000 af of UB beneficial use apportioned to Arizona. UB beneficial use does not include shared CRSP evaporation but includes evaporation from non-CRSP reservoirs and Navajo Reservoir. As a default, UB beneficial use is set to 5.76 maf, consistent with the formal yield determination of 2007HD, which represents the amount of water found to be legally available for consumptive use in the Upper Basin under the assumptions adopted by 2007HD. Note that Run 2 of 2007HD used a value of 5.79 maf for UB beneficial use so that value is used in validation. See section 4.1.

3.5 Quantification of Present Perfected Rights

Article VIII of the CRC exempts Present Perfected Rights (PPRs) from the apportionment and obligations set out in Article III, including the Article III(c) obligation. Kuhn (2012) offers an estimate of 2.267 maf for the amount of consumptive use associated with Upper Basin PPRs, based on work by the Upper Colorado River Commission. That value is the default used in the UBWB Model, but this may be changed by the user. This quantification does not account for extensive tribal water rights that might be considered like PPRs without yet having been put to use and that, once adjudicated and their senior priorities asserted, could substantially affect curtailments based on water right priorities. The UBWB Model constrains curtailments to protect UB beneficial use under PPRs.

3.6 Treatment of Arizona Upper Basin Beneficial Consumptive Use

Because the 50,000 af of UB beneficial use apportioned to Arizona by the UCRBC is not subject to curtailment, it is lumped with the quantification of PPRs described above.

3.7 Article III(c) Mexican Treaty Delivery Obligation

Article III(c) of the CRC sets out rules by which the annual 1.5 maf federal delivery obligation to Mexico should be apportioned between the Upper Division and Lower Division states. Interpretation of these provisions is controversial (Meyers, 1966; Kenney, 2012; MacDonnell, 2021b). The federal obligation is conventionally assumed to be equally apportioned between the Upper and Lower Divisions—that is the basis for the MOR in the LROC and has become the convention for simulation. Under a more severe interpretation, the Upper Division states may bear transit losses on its share of the delivery obligation and may thus owe more than 0.75 maf at Lee Ferry in some years (Wigington, 2019). On the other hand, under “surplus” conditions, the Upper Division may not be required to make any contribution to the federal obligation. Following the LROC a common simulation approach is to treat the Upper Division obligation as a constant annual volume of 0.75 maf. The UBWB Model currently lumps the 10-year cumulative volume of an equal share of the Mexico delivery, 7.5 maf, with the Lee Ferry flow obligation, adjusted to Lees Ferry. Future enhancements of the model code will separate the Upper Division share of the Mexico Obligation from the Article III(d) obligation to allow for more flexibility in simulating alternative policy assumptions. See Section 6.

3.8 Article III(d) Lee Ferry Flow Obligation and the Mexican Treaty Delivery Obligation

As a simplifying assumption, 2007HD treated the Article III(d) ten-year flow obligation on an annual basis 7.5 maf and lumped that obligation with an assumed quantification of the Upper Basin share of the Mexican delivery obligation of 0.75 maf per year, to create a composite annual flow obligation of 8.25 maf. This composite flow obligation was used in four runs to assess compliance with the Compact and the Mexican Treaty on a year-by-year basis. (2007HD also included four analyses that used a composite annual Lee Ferry flow obligation of 7.50 maf, reflecting an assumption that the Upper Basin will make no contribution to the federal delivery obligation to Mexico. See Table 1.) This year-by-year approach does not guarantee compliance with the cumulative obligation of Article III(d) but in none of those runs was the flow at Lee Ferry over a ten-year period allowed to fall below the implied ten-year composite cumulative flow obligation of 82.5 maf, thereby maintaining compliance with the

assumed cumulative flow obligation of Article III(d) and the assumed annual delivery obligation under the Mexican Treaty.

Although treating the Lee Ferry flow obligation on a year-by-year basis was sufficient for 2007HD, doing so will not assure compliance with the assumption of a ten-year cumulative flow obligation under more severe conditions. Accordingly, the UBWB Model assesses compliance with Article III(d) and Article III(c) by comparing the ten-year running sum of Lee Ferry flows against an assumed ten-year composite Lee Ferry flow obligation of 82.5 maf. Using this ten-year composite obligation simplifies the simulation, but limits flexibility for simulating alternative policy assumptions. This obligation can be changed by the user.

For consistency with inflow data sets based on flow at Lees Ferry, the lumped Article III(d) and (c) ten-year flow obligation was quantified as 82.3 maf at Lees Ferry, accounting for 20,000 acre-feet/year of intervening inflows from the Paria River, and Upper Basin compliance with that obligation was evaluated using Glen Canyon releases and spills (equivalent to Lees Ferry flows). These assumptions are consistent with most other analyses, including Reclamation (2007a, 2012), Paulson (2013) and CWCB (2012).

3.9 Glen Canyon Dam Release

The same simplifying assumptions for Lee Ferry flow obligations adopted for this analysis and 2007HD were made in establishing the minimum objective release (MOR) for Glen Canyon Dam as set out in Section II(2) of the LROC. The MOR is based on annualization of the Article III(d) obligation lumped with an assumed quantification of the Upper Basin's share of the federal Mexican delivery obligation for a total annual flow of 8.25 maf, as measured at Lee Ferry. Because Lee Ferry is located one mile below the mouth of the Paria River, which provides an average inflow of 20,000 af (0.02 maf), the MOR is set to 8.23 maf.

The LROC included provision for releases greater than the MOR to avoid spills at Glen Canyon Dam and to equalize storage in Lake Powell and Lake Mead (LROC, Sec II(3)). Operations at Glen Canyon Dam are currently conducted under the Interim Guidelines, which set out four operating tiers in Lake Powell and three operating tiers in Lake Mead. The lower three tiers at Lake Powell, collectively, allow for annual releases ranging from 7.0 maf to 9.5 maf, depending on the state of Lake Mead. When Lake Powell is in the upper, "Equalization Tier" releases greater than 9.5 maf could occur to equalize storage in the two reservoirs or to avoid spills.

Both the LROC and Interim Guidelines consider the level of Lake Mead in determining releases at Lake Powell; those provisions cannot be simulated in the UBWB Model. See Sections 5 and 6 for further discussion.

3.10 Curtailments

Curtailments are events where UB beneficial use must be reduced in a year in order to meet the assumed composite flow obligation at Lee Ferry. The calculation of the curtailment amount proceeds as follows: the model first calculates a water balance around the composite Upper Basin reservoir, assuming that any deficit in the 10-year Lees Ferry flow will be filled completely. Under this assumption it calculates the volume of water available for storage (*available_to_store* in Equation 1). If *available_to_store* is negative the curtailment is set as the minimum of the absolute value of *available_to_store* and the volume of non-PPR UB beneficial use. UB beneficial use is reduced by the amount of the curtailment and the water balance around the reservoir is recalculated (this does not change the final state of the reservoir, which in such cases is zero, so evaporation is unchanged) to determine the new value of Lees Ferry flows. The 10-year record of Lees Ferry flows is updated, and simulation moves to the next year.

3.11 Simulated Operation Assumptions

Table 3 shows the conceptual priority of annual outflows as adopted in the analysis (1 being the highest priority) (MacDonnell, 2021a; Reclamation, 2007a).

Table 3. Priority of Outflows

Priority	Outflow
1	Reservoir evaporation,
2	Upper Division consumptive use under PPRs and Arizona’s Upper Basin apportionment,
3	The Upper Division Article III(c) portion of the Mexican Treaty Water delivery obligation,
4	The Article III(d) 10-year Lee Ferry non-depletion obligation,
5	Upper Basin consumptive use under non-PPRs,
6	Glen Canyon minimum objective release, and
7	Reservoir storage.

Evaporation (Priority 1) is a physical constraint on water availability so is met before all other uses. The model does not protect against the case where the volume of water available to store is less than evaporation from an empty reservoir, which is 132877 af when simulating active capacity or 5,017 af when simulating live capacity.

UB beneficial use under Present Perfected Rights (Priority 2) is the highest water-use priority in the Basin.

Upper Division share of the federal obligation to Mexico (Priority 3) is independent from the Lee Ferry non-depletion obligation and will be required even in cases where the Lee Ferry flow obligation might be zero. However, in the current version of the model code the Articles III(c) and (d) obligations are lumped and treated at the same priority.

The Minimum Objective Release at Glen Canyon Dam under the LROC (Priority 6) is an operational objective that does not supersede the Compact and cannot force a curtailment of UB beneficial use. When Lake Powell is empty the Upper Division obligations under Article III(c) and Article III(d) will determine if any curtailment is necessary.

The model by default satisfies all Upper Basin consumptive use within the available physical and legal supply, regardless of the state of the reservoirs. While this assumption is not realistic—state water managers would certainly take actions to avoid a curtailment when reservoir storage dropped to alarming levels—it is tractable and appropriate for many studies. The UBWB Model code includes an implementation of a simple trigger system that may be used to simulate preemptive reductions in UB beneficial use.

4 Initial Simulations

Three initial simulations were conducted with the UBWB Model: Replication of Run 2 and Run 6 from 2007HD and a simulation of the 1200-year paleo reconstruction of natural flow at Lees Ferry by Meko et al. (2007). The outputs from these simulations are at Harding (2024b).

4.1 Replicating 2007HD

The UBWB Model has been validated against Run 2 and Run 6 from 2007HD. See Table 1. These runs were chosen because they simulated shortages, which made comparison more straightforward. The validation runs were conducted using the Lee Ferry natural flows from 2007HD, as these flows are different from those in Reclamation (2024) over the entire study period. The quantity of PPRs was set to zero, but this is a formality because the shortages calculated in the 2007 Hydrologic Determination did not reach the 2.267 maf level described earlier. Because the water balance is simply an accounting, if the code is correct any error will be driven solely by the differences in the evaporation models and will be very small.

The results of these simulations agreed very closely with the results for Run 2 and Run 6 published in Reclamation (2007a), with one exception. Shortages occurred in 1963, 1964, 1967, 1968 and 1977 in both runs under both models. The UBWB model replicated the shortages simulated by 2007HD in 1963, 1964, 1967, 1968

with a maximum difference of 0.02 percent, which was driven by slight differences between the evaporation models. The 1977 shortage was not replicated due to a conceptual difference between the two models. 1977 is the driest year in the natural flow record, with a volume of 5.5 maf. 2007HD simulated Upper Basin consumptive use as 5.79 maf and 5.98 maf in Run 2 and Run 6, respectively, and the validation runs in the UBWB Model did the same. In the case where inflow is insufficient to meet demand, the UBWB model reduces the Upper Basin consumptive use to equal the inflow, reflecting the physical reality. 2007HD does not do this, which results in larger shortages. The two models agree on the amount of consumptive use available to the Upper Basin, which is the difference between Upper Basin consumptive use demand and simulated shortages.

This process did not test the validity of mechanisms in the UBWB Model that were not exercised under the assumptions of Run 2. These mechanisms include protection of PPRs and conformance with the ten-year cumulative flow obligation at Lee Ferry. These mechanisms were validated by diagnosis and comparison to hand calculations.

4.2 Meko, 2007 Paleo Reconstruction

This simulation is forced with the 1244-year (762-2005) reconstruction of prehistoric natural flows at Lees Ferry reported in Meko, et al. (2007; treeflow.info, 2019) averaging 14.7 maf per year. This reconstruction is used in Appendix N of the *Final Environmental Impact Statement for the Colorado River interim guidelines for Lower Basin shortages and coordinated operations for Lake Powell and Lake Mead* (Reclamation, 2007b), the *Colorado River Water Availability Study, Phase I* (CWCB, 2012) and in the *Colorado River Basin Water Supply and Demand Study* (Reclamation, 2012a). Its use here facilitates comparison with those earlier reports. It is used here to test elements of the UBWB Model that were not exercised in the runs replicating the 2007HD runs, and outputs from this run are used as a benchmark against which to compare outputs from modified code.

The reconstructed flows from Meko et al. (2007) are based on a functional relationship between chronologies of tree-ring indices and historical natural flows. Meko et al. (2007) state that the reconstruction was based on flows at Lee Ferry (the compact point), and the supplemental information provided with the journal article describes the dataset as such, but data downloaded from the treeflow.info web site (Rice et al., 2009; treeflow.info, 2018) includes metadata that indicate that the reconstruction is based on natural flows at Lees Ferry. The reconstructed flows in both datasets are identical when rounded to the same precision. However, the data in both datasets labeled as observed flows are inconsistent between the two datasets and both are inconsistent with natural flows at either Lee Ferry or Lees Ferry in the current natural flow dataset from the U.S. Bureau of Reclamation (2024).

These inconsistencies, though not large, introduce some uncertainty with respect to the basis for the reconstruction. Based on information from one of the authors of Meko et al. (2007), the reconstruction has been assumed to be based on the Lees Ferry gage (Lucas, 2019).

Table 4 shows the duration, frequency and intensity of discrete curtailment spells. Discrete spells are events of a given duration that are separated from another event by at least one non-curtailment year.

Examination of the simulated reservoir conditions and curtailments showed that the time from a spill to a curtailment ranged from 12 to 73 years, with a mean of 35 years.

The transition matrix for curtailment/no curtailment based on the simulated conditions under the Meko (2007) trace is shown in Table 5. The probability of transitioning from the No Curtailment state to the Curtailment state is 2%, which is the same probability shown for all events in Table 4. If the current year is in a curtailment state, the probability of remaining in a curtailment state the next year is 54%. These probabilities are the result of the strong influence of the contents of Upper Basin storage on the likelihood of a curtailment.

Table 4. Discrete Curtailment Spells

Spell Length (years)	Events (#)	Average Intensity (maf)	Frequency (%/year)	Return Interval (years)
1	10	1.9	0.8	124
2	9	2.0	0.7	138
3	2	2.0	0.2	622
4	1	2.5	0.1	1244
5	1	2.4	0.1	1244
9	1	2.4	0.1	1244
all	24	2.1	2.0	52

Table 5. Curtailment Transition Matrix

	No Curtailment	Curtailment
No Curtailment	0.980	0.020
Curtailment	0.462	0.538

The model limitations discussed in Section 5 should be kept in mind when considering these results.

5 Model Limitations

The UBWB Model is subject to several limitations that should be considered when using its outputs.

5.1 Spatial and Temporal Averaging

The UBWB Model represents the water balance in the Upper Basin in its entirety on an annual basis and thereby represents average conditions across the basin and throughout the year. This lumped approach implies an assumption that any water use at any location in the basin and at any time of the year, has access to water that is anywhere in the basin, including Lake Powell. The result is that local physical shortages are not simulated, so the model overstates the level of consumptive use in the Upper Basin. This means that the model should not be used to represent true absolute values of Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use and curtailments. The model is valid for use in conducting sensitivity analyses that can inform about how a change in operation would affect curtailments and reservoir levels but results about how much those changes will affect basin conditions should be treated cautiously. This limitation can be mitigated through the use of an empirical model of Upper Basin beneficial consumptive use versus annual natural flow at Lees Ferry; see Section 6.

One way to interpret the results from the UBWB Model is that they show an estimate of the legal availability of water in the Upper Basin, which may not be achievable given the physical availability of water.

5.2 Coordinated Operation of Lake Powell and Lake Mead

The UBWB Model does not simulate Lake Mead, inflows below Lees Ferry, and water use in the Lower Basin. Therefore, it cannot simulate operations that are based on the relative contents or surface elevations in the two reservoirs. This includes the equalization provisions in the LROC and most operating criteria in any of the four tiers of the Interim Guidelines.

Though it cannot be known with certainty, it is unlikely that varying release volumes under the LROC or Interim Guidelines would significantly change the water balance at Lee Ferry, which will be constrained primarily by the Article III flow obligations at Lee Ferry.

The operating rules in both the LROC and Interim Guidelines allow releases above the MOR from Glen Canyon Dam to be triggered under some conditions by the level of Lake Mead. This can cause storage at Lake Powell to be reduced more than would otherwise be the case, and this could increase the frequency, duration or severity of a curtailment. Although the LROC or the Interim Guidelines are likely to have only a small effect on the water balance in the Upper Basin, understanding this effect has policy implications and the UBWB Model in its current configuration cannot inform that understanding.

5.3 Simulation of the Upper Basin Share of the Mexico Treaty Obligation

The UBWB Model simulates a constant annual delivery of 0.75 maf at Lee Ferry for the Upper Basin's contribution to the federal delivery obligation to Mexico. As noted in Section 1.3, quantification of the Upper Division's share is contentious. In adopting this simplifying assumption, the UBWB Model is no different than any other existing model of the Colorado River System. Nevertheless, the implications of different approaches to quantifying the Upper Division share of the Mexico obligation should be explored and the UBWB Model in its current configuration cannot easily do that.

6 Envisioned Enhancements to the UBWB Model

6.1 Upper Basin Beneficial Consumptive Use Model

An empirical model of beneficial consumptive use in the Upper Basin, including non-CRSP reservoirs, will be developed. The model will provide an estimate of the effect of local physical shortages on the nominal full beneficial consumptive use demand.

6.2 Expand Geographical Domain to Include the Lower Basin and the Flow into Mexico.

In the future, this model will be expanded to simulate Lake Mead, the gains between Lee Ferry and Lake Mead, and the tributaries below Lake Mead. This will allow simulation of the equalization provisions of the LROC and the tiered operating rules of the Interim Guidelines. While these operating rules probably will not have a large effect on the overall water balance in the Upper Basin, their simulation would allow an evaluation of how they might affect curtailments in the Upper Division. Simulation of Lake Mead and particularly the Lower Basin tributaries would also allow simulation of alternative quantifications of the Upper Basin obligation to provide a share of the Mexico Treaty delivery.

6.3 Separate Lake Powell from Other Upper Basin Reservoirs

Because the LROC and the Interim Guidelines condition releases from Lake Powell on its contents, simulating those operating rules will require separate simulations of Lake Powell and the reservoirs above it. This will require some additional simulation codes and a different evaporation model.

6.4 Network Simulation Method

Use of a network-flow algorithm would simplify the salient simulation routines because the network algorithm would represent connectivity and enforce mass balance, thus simplifying the code and its modification, and reducing errors. Using this approach as the basis for the system simulation will be investigated.

6.5 Validation Against CRSS Outputs

After the UBWB Model is extended as described in Section 6.2 it will be validated against output from a run of CRSS.

7 Code and Data Availability

The UBWB Model is implemented in Python 3. The code for the model and utilities, along with the data for the analyses described in Section 4 are available at Harding, 2024b.

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